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Appraisal of Stakeholders Engagement Strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company using Ratings and Gratifications by select Communities in ONELGA

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ABSTRACT

This study examines appraisal of stakeholder engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company with a view to finding out the rating and gratifications. To achieve this, this study raised five (5) objectives which are to; find out the stakeholders engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company; investigate the connect between stakeholders engagement strategy and stakeholders expectations; appraise if the stakeholders engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company (NAOC) is in line with conventional practices. This study was anchored on two theories; stakeholder theory and corporate social responsibility theory. The study adopted the survey research design with questionnaire and interview guide as instruments for data gathering. The population of the study comprised of two streams of universe, first is the staff of Nigeria Agip Oil Company which is 6,621 while selected communities in ONELGA, Obrikom and Obagi is 350,000. Therefore, the total population of the study is 356,621. Taro Yamane sample size determination formula was used to arrive at sample size of 400. Data obtained from the instruments were analysed using Weighted Mean Score (four point Likert scale). Findings of this study showed that the Nigerian Agip Oil Company designed its stakeholders' engagement strategy to accommodate the company and the host communities. The finding of this study showed that there is a connect between stakeholders' engagement strategy and stakeholders' expectations because it addressed the expectations of the people. Based on the strength of the findings, the study concluded that the Nigerian Agip Oil Company designed its stakeholders' engagement strategy to accommodate the company and the host communities. The study also concluded that there is a connect between stakeholders' engagement strategy and stakeholders expectations because it addressed the expectation of the people. The study recommended that there is need for companies and organizations to have a formidable stakeholders engagement strategy that will impact on the company and host communities. The study also recommended that it is good and relevant for an organizations stakeholders' engagement strategy to have a connection with stakeholders expectations by addressing the MOU between the company and the host communities.

Keywords: Appraisal, Stakeholders, Engagement, Strategy, Nigerian Agip Oil Company, Ratings, Gratifications, select Communities, ONELGA

INTRODUCTION

Engaging stakeholders is crucial for successful strategic planning in organizations. It involves identifying, understanding and involving people who have a stake in the outcome of the plan. Hence, effective stakeholders engagement strategy requires a comprehensive approach that includes ongoing communication, listening and collaboration.

Stakeholders engagement strategy is a process that organizations or companies can follow with, or inform (or a combination of all three) their existing stakeholders. This process entails identifying, mapping and prioritizing stakeholders to determine the best tactics for effective communication while making the best use of available resources. Stakeholders engagement helps companies to proactively consider the needs and desires of anyone who has a stake in their company, which can foster connections, trust, confidence and buy-in for the organization's key initiatives.

According to Paulin (2020) when well done, stakeholders engagement strategy can mitigate potential risks and conflicts with stakeholders groups, including uncertainty, dissatisfaction, misalignment, disengagement and resistance to change. Also, when it comes to strategic planning, stakeholders engagement is critical. Thus, it is important that the company's stakeholders understand why the company exist, where the company want to go and how the company will achieve all its objectives. Moreso, Nzebechi (2019) posits that it is essential that the key stakeholders are aligned with and brought into the strategic direction of the company so that they can become advocates that can help the company achieve its mission and vision. Also, Nzebechi (2019) added that it is important for the company's stakeholders to have a wealth of relevant knowledge and experience that the management may want to take into consideration to help the company become more impactful, sustainable and viable over the long-term.

This is because according to Chigonim (2021) stakeholders are specific groups of people (not the general public) each with different desires and needs from the organization. A stakeholder is anyone who has a stake in your organization or company either through interest, influence or both. Stakeholders can range from shareholders to staff, board members, volunteers, funders, government, customers, host communities and beyond.

Furthermore, Njoku (2020) posits that stakeholders and publics are different subsets and require different communication strategies. While specific members of the public maybe stakeholders, not all of them are. This is because the public are either unaware or aware of the company but may lack both interest and influence at this stage, although some public are essentially aware publics, that have the potential to become future stakeholders.

Moreso, Dooms (2019: 64) notes that the oil and gas industry is regarded as a very dynamic industrial sector and involves numerous activities that may be viewed by companies operating there especially the Nigerian Agip Oil Company from several perspectives. These could include social, political, legal, environmental, technological, economic and commercial viewpoints. In addition, Lester (2007) states that the type and interest of stakeholders are of immense importance to the organizations as these can be utilized to enhance performance from corporate business and operational perspectives. Thus, stakeholders identification and categorization is the most significant step in stakeholders engagement and it is classified into two categories; direct (primary) stakeholders and indirect (secondary) stakeholders.

According to Lester (2007) direct stakeholders are entities that play a visible role in a particular venture and are impacted by it, while indirect stakeholders are those not involved in the venture but interested in it and inclined to monitor its progress. In the context of oil and gas operations, the direct stakeholders will include the oil and gas company, host community, government (both local and national).

The thrust however, is to appraise the stakeholders engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company with a view to streamlining the rating and gratifications among constituents.

Statement of the Problem

Stakeholders engagement strategy has been a topic of debate in the Niger Delta and in particular, the oil-rich communities playing host to Nigerian Agip Oil Company in ONELGA, Rivers State. Activities of crude oil exploration commenced in ONELGA in 1966 and these activities were carried by Nigerian Agip Oil Company in the region for a period of over 50 years now. How this is rated among the host

communities remains a cause for great concern. Moreso, the gratifications these communities drives from such activities becomes a questions begging for answer. Observations point to the negative impact of oil production activities.

This has become most pertinent bearing in mind the fact that the communities are restive being that oil and gas are constantly extracted from their soil.

Over the last two decades, the Nigerian Agip Oil Company has suffered enormous loses because of recurrent conflicts with local communities in the area. Conflict situations have resulted variously in the suspension of oil operation the deferment of production and even cut backs in production. The implications of these developments have been far reaching, reducing profits and prompting higher cost as a result of the sabotage of oil facilities; the occasional payment of collateral damage associated with vandalism of equipment; even the payment of ransom to secure the release of kidnapped staff. Thus, the progressive breakdown in the relationship between the company and the local communities within which they are based is a problem not only for the Nigerian Agip Oil Company which relies on the revenue from oil but also the local communities. The concerns of these study are therefore perceived in the foregoing.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed at evaluating stakeholders engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company with a view to finding out the rating and gratifications if this strategy is perceived by the host communities. The specific objectives are to;

7. find out the stakeholders engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company
8. investigate the connect between stakeholders engagement strategy and stakeholders expectations.
9. Appraise if the stakeholders engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company (NAOC) is in line with conventional practices.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on two theories; stakeholder theory and corporate social responsibility theory.

2.1.1 Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory originated from four key academic fields: sociology, economics, politics, and ethics (Mainardes *et al.* , 2011). In particular, it derived from the study of management practices (Slinger, 1999) while the use of the term grew out of the pioneering work at Stanford Research Institute (SRI) in the 1960s. The stakeholder idea, which emerged from the SRI, was presented in a report on planning circulated to a group of business subscribers in 1963 (Slinger, 1999). In the report the concept of stakeholder was described in terms of creative judgment, intuitive reasoning, and involvement of people in all of a business's relationship (Slinger, 1999). The SRI pointed out that managers needed to understand the interests and concerns of shareholders, employees, customers, suppliers, lenders and society, in order to develop objectives that they would support (Freeman and McVea, 2005). The SRI, thus defined stakeholders as "those groups without whose support the organisation would cease to exist" (cited in Freeman, 1984:13). With the view that the long-term success of organisation depended on the support of such groups, the SRI asserted that management should actively explore its relationship with all its stakeholders (Freeman and McVea, 2005).

Drawing on corporate planning, systems theory, corporate social responsibility and organisational theory literatures, Freeman (1984) crystallized the stakeholder concept into a framework for strategic management in the mid-1980s. According to Freeman (1984:5) "...current theories are inconsistent with both the quantity and kinds of change which are occurring in the business environment of the 1980s... A new conceptual framework is needed". The stakeholder approach thus grew out of the failure of traditional strategy frameworks to equip managers to deal with the rapid changes in their business environment, particularly the nonmarket environment (Freeman and McVea, 2005).

Based on the inclusive viewpoint of the stakeholder theory, an enterprise exists at the meeting point of a variety of interests. The theory portrays a position in an intricate web of social relationships of dependency and expectation. Overall corporate success from management's viewpoint is determined solely by the level of satisfaction enjoyed and displayed by the various sections and components of the

stakeholder group. This viewpoint demands that stakeholders are properly identified and treated appropriately and respectfully to ensure optimal satisfaction for the various segments of the stakeholder group. Affirming this view, Crilly and Sloan (2012) identified attention to stakeholders as a strategic management issue which has the capacity to potentially affect the achievement of overall corporate goals either positively or negatively depending on how matters relating to stakeholders are handled. CSR, as pointed out by Khan, Latif, Jalal, Anjum, and Rizwan (2014), places the overall superior responsibility to the business's stakeholders by the managers of the business. The analogy by the aforementioned authors portrays the attribution of complete business supremacy of management control on the shoulders of the major stakeholders who are the owners of business. The major task of managers, therefore, is to identify stakeholders and stakeholder groups, especially those who share a common interest. It is important to determine their level of power and treat them appropriately with a view to winning them to management's side totally and giving them maximum satisfaction by harnessing a balanced link between the business and the natural, social and financial environments (Carroll & Buchholtz, 2014). Stakeholder theory in management is closely and inseparably attached to the theory, principles, and practice of CSR in every organization, and particularly in the oil and gas companies operating in the Nigerian Niger Delta.

The Corporate Social Responsibility Theory

This theory was propounded by Milton Friedman. The theory states that people will make decisions on spending based on what we think our income will be over time. What Friedman (1970) called our 'permanent income', and not just our current income which may be higher.

Furthermore, Friedman (1970) opines that for free trade, smaller government and a slow, steady increase of money supply in a growing economy. Also, according to Wragg (1975), the social responsibility of business is to increase profits. This is an appropriate starting point for a discussion on the responsibility of business towards society. Companies if on one side, within the globalization and the economic development, have increased their scale and scope and brought an unprecedented benefit for the public (creating jobs, wealth and motivations...), on the other side may have also resulted in collective negative effects (so called externalities) such as environmental degradation, exploration, exploitation of labour, financial sector instability to name a few.

Thus, this theory is relevant to this study because, it talks about synergy and interconnection within and outside the organisation and that organisation must put a communication structure that will guide it to achieve its stakeholders engagement strategy.

Conceptual Framework

Oil & Gas Management Trends

In 2014 Nigeria's average oil production was estimated at 2.21 million barrels per day (mbpd) and 2.31 mbpd and 2.18 mbpd in 2012 and 2013 respectively. With a maximum crude oil production of 2.5 mbpd in 2015⁶, Nigeria ranks as Africa's largest producer of oil and the sixth largest producing country in the world. The exploration and production activities leave inevitably impacts on the environment and humans. Impacts on the environment have debilitating effect on the host communities who depends solely on ecosystem resources and biological diversity of their area for sustenance.

Oil wealth is to be used for development. Development is considered to be sustainable when it "meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their own needs". In this instance the present needs of the host communities are far from being meet. The declaration of the World Summit on Sustainable Development, held in Johannesburg in 2002, assumes a collective responsibility to advance and strengthen "the interdependence and mutually reinforcing pillars of sustainable development – economic development, social development and environmental protection at local, regional and global levels". Sustainable local development hinges on improving the quality of life of the local population, with a transition towards meeting their basic needs; reducing hunger and poverty. Sustainability issues are becoming more complex and interrelated with other dimensions of human life. The dimensions of the Human Development Index (income, education and

health) are used to determine the main outcomes of sustainable development which are now to replace the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs).

The SWOT Analysis in Oil and Gas Industry

Tavana *et al.* (2011) assessed different direct ways of oil and gas export from the Caspian Sea to the world markets. They applied the Delphi method as well as the SWOT analysis to assess the alternative strategies for choosing the ways. Xingang *et al.* (2013) exploited the SWOT analysis for developing the Chinese shale gas status. Four types of productivity development strategies for this industry were formulated based on the SWOT analysis. Khan (2018) used the SWOT analysis to evaluate the environment of CNG industry. Nine strategies were considered by using the SWOT analysis to understand the growth rate of Iranian CNG market. Subsequently, a fuzzy goal programming approach was used to evaluate those strategies. Azubuike *et al.* (2018) identified the main policies and legal issues for shale gas development in Algeria. The internal key factors (weaknesses and strengths) and external key factors (opportunities and threats) were taken into consideration. Hajizadeh (2019) took advantage of the machine learning technology in the oil and gas industry. The SWOT analysis was applied to manage the strategies for technology enablement.

Government Policies and the Implications for the Oil Industry

Jones (1995) rightly observes that government policy often affects firm/stakeholder relationships. The laws that govern the oil industry have in many ways served to aggravate the relationship between the oil companies and communities that are affected by their operations. The economy of Nigeria being largely dependent on revenue from oil export, the government, particularly at the federal level determined the boundaries of oil exploration and production activities through decrees and laws promulgated by military regimes headed by the Northerners. What is most interesting about the laws governing the oil industry is how similar they are to those employed by the British colonial government when the country was a colony. For example, Section 1 of the Mineral Ordinance of 1945 provides that the entire property and control of all minerals and mineral oil, in, under, or upon any land in Nigeria, and of all her rivers, streams, and water course throughout Nigeria, is and shall be vested in the CROWN (cited in Omoruyi, 2002:2).

The Petroleum Act of 1969, which provides a legal supportive framework for oil operations post-independence stipulates that the entire ownership and control of all petroleum in, under or upon any lands to which this section applies shall be vested in the State. This section applies to all land (including land covered by water) which is in Nigeria; under the territorial waters of Nigeria, or forms part of the continental shelf..." (Petroleum Act, 1969) The implication of the Petroleum Act of 1969 is that individuals, communities, local governments and even states with land containing minerals were denied their rights to the minerals.

Furthermore, in 1978, the Land Use Act was enacted, which states that, "Subject to the provisions of this Act, all land comprised in the territory of each State in the Federation are vested in the Governor of that State and such land shall be held in trust and administered for the use and common benefit of Nigerians in accordance with the provisions of this Act" (Deinduomo, 2009). The implication of this Act is that the Governor of the State is empowered to revoke a customary or statutory right of occupancy, respectively, "for the requirement of the land for mining purposes or pipelines or for any purposes connected therewith" (Section 28:2:c and 28:3:b).

Concept of Stakeholder

We believe at this point it is important to take a step back and raise one, crucial question: what we precisely mean by "stakeholder"? The earliest definition is often credited to an internal memo produced in 1963 by the Stanford Research Institute.

Those groups without whose support the organization would cease to exist" (Freeman, 1984; Friedman & Miles, 2006; Mitchell *et al.*, 1997). Similar definitions have been advocated by Bowie (1988), (Freeman & Reed, 1983), and Näsi (1995). (Freeman *et al.*, 2004) has continued to use this definition in a modified form: "those groups who are vital to the survival and success of the organization". This type of definition,

which is entirely organization-centric, is stringent in the sense that it excludes categories of agents that other definitions include (Friedman & Miles, 2006). For example, in what is commonly regarded, at least in academic circles, as seminal stakeholder texts, stakeholders are defined as “any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organization objectives” (Freeman, 1984; Friedman & Miles, 2006).

For the purpose of this dissertation we will stick with this latter definition provided by Freeman (1984), although we recognize the need for a compromise between a very broad and a very narrow approach to the delineation of the appropriate range of relevant stakeholders. We appreciate this definition because, although being one of the broadest in literature, leaves the notion of stake and the field of possible stakeholders open, giving full discretion to the organization in the phase of stakeholder identification (this phase will be covered in details in Section 3.2.2).

For Bryson (2004) in this definition the term refers to persons, groups or organizations that must somehow be taken into account by leaders, managers and front-line staff. This definition is intentionally broad: Freeman’s objective was to develop a literary device that calls into question the emphasis on shareholders (Sundaram & Inkpen, 2004). Clearly, such a broad definition raises some practical concerns.

Perspectives on the Stakeholder Approach

Donaldson and Preston (1995) identified three ways in which the stakeholder theory is viewed: normative/prescriptive, instrumental, and descriptive/empirical. Each of these perspectives are discussed in the following sections, with more focus on the descriptive focus as the present study is particularly interested in shedding further light on how firms employ the stakeholder approach, whether they use it to achieve purely strategic/instrumental ends, and whether the instrumental agendas or uses are driven by normative values or not. The author views the normative and instrumental uses of the stakeholder approach as the main thrust of the stakeholder theory, and argues that the descriptive use of the stakeholder theory holds the key to the advancement of the theory and practice of stakeholder management because it empirically reveals not only the practical implications of employing or adopting a stakeholder approach, it allows us to know whether instrumental or normative objectives drive stakeholder management processes. The question of the practicality or effectiveness of the instrumental or normative use of the stakeholder approach is not just an academic one; it is a question that practitioners are confronted with in the real world. There is a perceived gap between stakeholder theory and stakeholder management practice. The descriptive use of the stakeholder theory provides a platform for bridging the gap between the theoretical analysis and the practical implications of the concept. The relevance of the stakeholder approach is dependent not only on its theoretical robustness, but on its practicality. In line with this thinking, Freeman (1984) states, “good management theories are practical, that is, they are relevant to practicing managers.” Similarly, Friedman and Miles (2006) note that the development of a theory is dependent on its ability to influence management practices and policies and vice versa. With this brief introduction, the discussion now turns to the three main uses of the stakeholder approach.

Stakeholder Engagement

Over the recent years, corporations engaging with stakeholders other than the companies’ shareholders has increasingly become popular. Before examining the element, a brief explanation of the term ‘stakeholder’ is important. Stakeholders can be generally defined as those who can affect and be affected by corporations - in financial or non-financial terms. There are three attributes of stakeholders, of which all stakeholders possess at least one. Firstly, the stakeholder must have the ability to exercise some power within its relationship with the corporation. Secondly, the relationship between the corporation and the firm should be considered as legitimate or at least socially desirable. Finally, the claim the stakeholder has on the corporation must be considered as urgent in that it is crucial in nature to the shareholder or that it is time-sensitive. This approach illustrates that all stakeholders are not viewed as equal in the eyes of corporations. Stakeholders who possess all three characteristics are referred to as ‘definitive

stakeholders' and their claims are usually prioritized by corporations due to the profound consequences that occur when they are neglected.

The two types of under this term are Primary and Secondary stakeholders. The primary stakeholders come in forms of internal parties, such as employees and external parties, such as communities, who enjoy a direct interest in the business or company, while secondary stakeholders are the public and special interest groups, and competitors, who by contrast have an indirect interest in the business or company. Within the context of CSR in the oil industry, it is necessary for the external parties (local communities) to be regarded as an important stakeholder, due to the potentially negative impact of the operations and practices on these communities. For the purposes of this research, the term "stakeholder" refers to the public solely.

The phases of stakeholder engagement

In this section we will start analysing what is stakeholder engagement from a theoretical stand point and which is its role in relation to strategies and reporting. We believe involvement of stakeholder is important because it provides crucial data and information which can be useful both for effectively managing an organization and for determining the most relevant and material topics to be covered in the organization's integrated or sustainability report. In fact, as argued by Friedman and Miles (2006), there are many reasons large enterprises devote resources to stakeholder engagement.

Stakeholder theory scholars have tried to classify the relational models between corporations and stakeholders assuming different gradual paths of the stakeholders' involvement (Manetti, 2011; Svendsen, 1998; Waddock, 2008). We opted to summarize the overall process of stakeholder engagement in the following three phases:

1. **Stakeholder Identification and Analysis:** In a first stage, organizations need to identify and analyse the characteristics of each group of stakeholders, understanding how these groups can affect and/or are affected by the organization. Moreover, in this phase it is necessary to study how the engagement of stakeholders affect the risk management of the enterprise. We refer to these steps as the "Stakeholder identification and analysis" phase.
2. **Interaction With Stakeholders:** Secondly, the corporations try to manage stakeholders' expectations and the social and economic issues that they support and begin to find a way for balancing their positions (Manetti, 2011). This phase sees the implementation of the stakeholder engagement strategy and it is where the interaction with stakeholders actually takes place. Corporations involve their stakeholders in decision-making processes, making them participants in the business management, sharing information, dialoguing and creating a model of mutual responsibility (Manetti, 2011).
3. **Evaluation and Reporting:** The third phase is not necessarily to intend as the final stage. Its steps concern the measurement of the stakeholder engagement performances and outcome and the report of data to be useful for consequent redefinition of the process: thus, these operations are to be performed along the whole process and are useful to further develop next iterations of stakeholder engagement activities.

Stakeholders Influence and Firms' Response Strategies

The preceding section discussed attributes that qualified groups or individuals as stakeholders, and the role of managers in determining stakeholder salience. Mitchell *et al.*'s (1997) stakeholder identification and salience framework, which has been empirical tested by a few scholars, provides an organisational perspective of stakeholder identification and salience, focusing on those who can affect the organisation. Thus, while the preceding section highlights important stakeholder attributes that can facilitate stakeholder identification, this section identifies and discusses specific strategies stakeholders employ in order to influence organisations, as well as other stakeholder characteristics that draw the attention of firms and their managers, and the strategies firms adopt in response to these stakeholder strategies and characteristics.

Until Freeman's seminal work (1984), strategists such as Porter (1980) ignored the impact of stakeholders on the formulation and implementation of strategy, advocating that industry structure alone determines an appropriate strategy. Freeman took Porter's five forces model for analysis (competitiveness, relative power of customers and suppliers, and the threat of substitutes and new entrants) and added a further dimension: the relative power of stakeholders and their potential to cooperate with or threaten corporate strategy (Freeman, 1984). A few scholars have attempted to identify specific strategies stakeholders adopt in their bid to influence the behaviour of firms. The earliest attempt at understanding how stakeholders actually affected the organisation was the work associated with Vogel's (1978), which focused on strategies such as proxy resolutions and boycotts. In recent years other researchers have focused on shareholder resolution (Thompson and Davis, 1997) and modified vendettas (Corlett, 1989, Shipp, 1987).

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

The major role and aim of companies that exist in the modern world is to have and sustain positive economic impacts. Usually these corporations perform actions and make decisions that have detrimental effects on the surrounding communities and the environment, with the latter further negatively impacting the communities. Due to these negative impacts, there is a justified increasing pressure upon these companies to behave in ways that are responsible and to distribute benefits to a wide range of stakeholders. CSR is one of the key mechanisms used in achieving this aim.

The CSR concept has gained importance in the recent decades and has impacted companies in ways which have practical significance to businesses across the world. There have been several attempts to establish a more robust and well-rounded definition of CSR for better understanding, as there are several individually biased definitions that exist. It has been defined as the continuing commitment of a business to contribute to sustainable economic development and to behave ethically while improving the quality of life of the workforce and their families, as well as the local community and society at large. It has also been defined as operating an organization in a manner that meets and exceeds the legal, public, commercial, and ethical expectations that society has of the enterprise. Social responsibility is and should perpetually be a guiding principle for every decision made in every aspect of the organization. The CSR concept can also be defined as a principle stating that corporations should be accountable for the effects of any of their actions on their community or environment. The approaches to implementing CSR initiatives will be shown in Nigerian Petroleum Industry context in the subsequent chapter. A brief definition of the main categories is required, however. The categories are: (i) voluntary and (ii) regulated initiatives.

Categories of Corporate Social Responsibility

Giami, Orji, and Worgu (2015) viewed CSR from the perspective of accountability and referred to CSR as corporate social accounting and for that reason classified CSR into various genres as identified both in the upstream and downstream sectors of the oil and gas industry in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. Giami *et al.* (2015) declared that the various types of CSR prevalent in practice in the area are classified into multiple facets. These aspects or facets of CSR are deliberated.

Redemptive CSR is aimed at redeeming a struggling and dishonored corporate image and usually arises from fallouts of a crisis situation and not usually voluntary on the part of the company. Advocacy CSR is usually connected to advocacy and promotional campaigns by organizations, associations, and societies not affiliated or related to government. Community-participatory CSR is usually initiated by the community and so it is people oriented and rests on community support. Mass media-induced CSR comes about due to criticisms, sarcasm, and pressures from mass media publications on the social irresponsiveness of the operating companies in the area.

Corporate Social Responsibility and the Environment

One of the central issues that CSR seeks to address is that of the environment. For many decades there has been abundant initiatives directed at the preservation of the environment (Nedelko & Potocan, 2014). There are three fundamental features of CSR as perceived by citizens. These features are environment,

economic, and social. While studying the impact of seismic and production activities on the mangrove systems of the Nigerian Niger Delta, Osuji *et al.* (2006) provided evidence of the immense devastation brought upon the environment and the ecosystem of the region. Similarly, Allen (2014) and Olaniyi and Omo-Irabor (2016) stressed the fact of this impact as immediate evidence for the urgent need for oil and gas prospecting and producing companies to do more in repairing the environment in which they operate. The level of environmental degradation in the area signifies to a larger extent the failure by government to enforce environmental policies on oil and gas formulated for the attainment of sustainable development (Allen, 2014). So far, there appears to be a perception by the landowners that not much seem to have been done in the direction of striking a balance between corporate profit goals and environmental and societal sustenance by the oil and gas corporations.

Empirical Review

Jim and Peter (2004) carried out a study entitled: Stakeholder engagement strategy of Shell Petroleum Development Company (SDPC) in Niger Delta Region. Their objective was to find out the experience of shell petroleum development Company in stakeholder engagement. The survey research design, interview guide and questionnaire as research instruments were adopted. The population of the study was 1,200 while the sample size was 230. The finding of the study showed that shell petroleum development company suffered deep frustrations occasioned by inappropriate and ineffective stakeholders' engagement.

The findings of the study also revealed that aside from making host community encounter repeated, deprivations, the SPDC in the Niger Delta failed adequately involved host communities in its corporate social responsibility practices for stakeholders' engagements to address communities that perennially suffer the negative impacts of business activities.

The concluded that shell petroleum company suffered deep frustrations occasioned by inappropriate and effective stakeholders engagement. The study also concluded that aside from making host communities encounter repeated deprivations, the SPDC in the Niger Delta failed adequately involve host communities in its corporate social responsibility practices for stakeholders' engagements to address communities that perennially suffer the negative impacts of business activities. The study therefore recommended that multinational companies such as SPDC should apply their stakeholders' engagement programmes in a way that will benefit all the stakeholders. The study also recommends that multinational companies should involve their host communities in their stakeholders' engagement practices.

Mathew (2020) carried out a study entitled stakeholders engagement strategy of total energies Nigeria Ltd" ratings and gratifications by select communities ONELGA. The objective was to find out how the stakeholders engagement strategy has fared in its dealings with host communities in ONELGA, Rivers State. The survey research design, interview guide and questionnaire were used as research instruments. The population of the study was 800,000 while the sample size was 400.

The findings of the study showed that an effective means of establishing sustainable cordial relationship with host communities in ONELGA is by involving them in the ownership operations in their place. The findings of the study also showed that the relationship between Total Energies Nigeria Limited and host communities in ONELGA, Rivers State can be sustained if both parties work collaboratively to determine ways in which benefits from the operations may be maximized.

The study concluded that effective means of establishing sustainable cordial relationships with host communities in ONELGA is by involving them in the ownership operations in their communities. The study also concluded that the relationship between Total Energies Nigeria Limited and their host communities in ONELGA, Rivers State can be sustainable if both parties work collaboratively to determine ways in benefits from the operations may be maximized.

The study therefore, recommended that Total Energies Nigeria Limited and other multinational companies operating in ONELGA, should recognized the significance of effectively engaging with and managing affairs with host communities where oil and gas operations are situated. The study also recommended that Total Energies Nigeria Limited and other companies operating in the area should

implement development of stakeholders engagement polices and strategies towards establishing sustainable cordial relationships with host communities in ONELGA, Rivers State.

Peters and Person (2021) carried out a study entitled stakeholders engagement of oil and gas industries in Nigeria: rating and gratification by select communities in EMOLGA. Their objective were to find out the nature of stakeholders engagement strategy of oil and gas companies operating in Emohua Local Government Area, Rivers State. The survey research design, interview guide and questionnaire were used as data gathering instruments. The population of the study was 650,000 while the sample size was 400.

The findings of the study showed that main stakeholders are the local community group, contactors and local authorities therefore the main motivations for engaging is to understand stakeholders expectations and to identify sustainability issues that companies are facing. The findings of the study also showed that stakeholder engagement strategy is considered as an effective vehicle that help to carry out the proper decision-making for obtaining and showing of gratification by increasing the degree of harmonization and enhance the overall performance of the organization. The study concluded that the main stakeholder are the local community group, contractors and local authorities hence the motivations for engagement is understand stakeholders expectations and to identifying sustainability issues that the oil and gas companies in area are facing. The study also concluded that stakeholders engagement strategy is an effective vehicle that helps to carry out the proper decision making for obtaining and showing of gratifications by increasing the degree of harmonization that generate appropriate decisions. The study therefore, recommended that effective stakeholders engagement can be achieved to create and information sharing platform clarifying valuable knowledge and insights at an early stage in the policy development process. The study also recommended that the oil and gas companies should engage in more empowerment and motivations that makes stakeholders feel respected and valued having the opportunity to directly influence policies that impact their lives and those the represent.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the survey research design with questionnaire and interview guides as instrument for data collection. The population of the study consist of two streams of universe, first is the staff of Nigeria Agip Oil Companies and selected communities in ONELGA, Obrikom and Ogbagi which is 356,621 and Taro Yamane sample size determination formula was used to arrive at the sample size of 400 used for the study. Questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection and purposive sampling technique to administer the instrument to the respondents. Data obtained from the questionnaire was analysed using weighted means scores (four points likert scale). The score of 2.5 was used as the criterion for discussion. A response which is equal to or more than 2.5 is positive, i.e the respondents agree with the item while any mean response less than 2.5 was negative.

Table 1: Stakeholder Engagement Strategies of Nigerian Agip Oil Company

S/N	Agreement Level	Respondent's Mean Score					TOTAL	MEAN	DECISION
		SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1				
1	Community development programs (ICPs): Health education, infrastructure project	250	90	30	20	390	3.46	Accepted	
		1000	270	60	20	1,350			
2.	Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives: Scholarships, empowerment programmes	200	100	60	30	390	3.20	Accepted	
		800	300	120	30	1,250			
3	Stakeholder engagement forums: Regular meetings with community leaders	230	100	50	10	390	3.41	Accepted	
		920	300	100	10	1,330			
4	Grievance mechanism: Established process for addressing community concerns	270	80	20	20	390	3.53	Accepted	
		1,080	240	40	20	1,350			

Criterion Mean = 2.5

Data in the table 1 above shows the stakeholders engagement strategies of Nigerian Agip Oil Company

Table 2: The Link between Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Stakeholders' Expectation

S/N	Agreement Level	Respondent's Mean Score				TOTAL	MEAN	DECISION
		SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1			
1	Yes there is a connection between stakeholders engagement strategy and stakeholders expectation	210	110	40	30	390	3.28	Accepted
		840	330	80	30	1,280		
2.	There is often a connection between stakeholders engagement strategy and stakeholders expectation	200	130	30	30	390	3.28	Accepted
		800	390	60	30	1,280		
3	There is rarely a connection between stakeholders engagement strategy and stakeholder expectations	20	10	140	220	390	1.56	Rejected
		80	30	280	220	610		
4	There is no connection between stakeholders engagement strategy and stakeholders expectations	20	20	150	200	390	1.64	Rejected
		80	60	300	200	640		

Criterion Mean = 2.5

Data in table 2 above shows that there is a connect between stakeholders engagement strategy and stakeholders expectations.

Table 3: The Stakeholder Strategy and Conventional Practices

S/N	Agreement Level	Respondent's Mean Score					TOTAL	MEAN	DECISION
		SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1				
1	Yes the stakeholder engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company is in line with conventional practices	250	100	20	20	390			
		1000	300	40	20	1,360	3.48	Accepted	
2.	The stakeholders engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company is often in libne with conventional practices	240	100	30	20	390			
		960	300	60	20	1,340	3.43	Accepted	
3	The stakeholders engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company is rarely in line with conventional practices	10	20	130	230	390			
		40	60	390	230	720	1.84	Rejected	
4	The stakeholders engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company is not in line with conventional practices	25	25	120	220	390			
		100	75	240	220	635	1.62	Rejected	

Criterion Mean = 2.5

Data in table 3 above shows that the stakeholders engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company is in line with conventional practices

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Research Question 1: how is the stakeholder Engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company?

Findings of this study showed that the Nigerian Agip Oil Company designed its stakeholder's engagement strategy to accommodate the company and the host communities. Findings of this study is in agreement with the principles of the stakeholder theory which states that the concept of stakeholder was described in terms of creative judgment intuitive reasoning and involvement of people in all business relationship. Findings of this study also is in agreement with the principles of the corporate social responsibility theory which states that people will make decision on spending based on what we thing our income will be over-time. Finding of this study is in agreement with the earlier study carried out by Jim

and Peter (2004) whose study revealed that Shell Petroleum development company suffered deep frustrations, occasioned by in appropriate and ineffective stakeholders' engagement. Findings of this study is also in agreement with the earlier study carried out by Matthew (2020) whose study revealed that an effective means of establishing sustainable cordial relationship with host communities on ONELGA is by involving them in the ownership operations in their place.

Research Question 2: What is the connect between stakeholder engagement strategy and stakeholder expectations?

The finding of this study showed that there is a connect between stakeholders' engagement strategy and stakeholders expectations because it addressed the expectation of the people. Finding of this study is in agreement with the principles of the stakeholder theory which states that the theory is a highly-disputed theory and the contestability makes it very challenging and problematic. The theory is not a single theory, but a combination of diverse narratives. Finding of this study more so, corroborate with the corporate social responsibility theory which states that the theory talks about synergy and interconnection within and outside the organization and that organization must put a communication structure that will guide it to achieve its stakeholder engagement strategy. Findings of this study is in agreement with the earlier study carried out by Peter and Person (2021) whose study revealed that the main stakeholders are the local community, group, contractors and local authorities therefore, the main motivation for engaging is to understand stakeholders expectations and to identify sustainability issues that companies are facing. Findings of this study more so, corroborates with the earlier study carried out by Jim and Peter (2004) whose study revealed that aside from making host community encounter repeated, deprivations, the SPDC in the Niger Delta failed adequately involved host communities in its corporate social responsibility practices for stakeholders engagement to address communities that perennially suffer the negative impacts of business activities.

Research Question 3: To what extent is the stakeholders' engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company (NAOC) in line with conventional practices?

The finding of this study showed that stakeholders' engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company is in line with conventional practices. Finding of this study is in agreement with the principles of the stakeholder theory which states that the theory requires organizations to develop expertise in the understanding of how stakeholders groups emerge, the key issues of concern, and the extent they are willing to go to either enable or prevent the organization from achieving its objectives as a result of these issues. Finding of this study is also in agreement with the principles of the corporate social responsibility theory which states that the social responsibility of business is to increase profit. This is an appropriate starting point for a discussion on the responsibility of business toward society. Finding of this study is in agreement with the earlier study carried out by Matthew (2020) whose study revealed that the relationship between Total Energies Nigeria Limited and host communities in ONELGA, Rivers State can be sustainable if both parties work collaboratively to determine ways in benefits from the operations may be maximized. The findings of this study more so, is in agreement with the earlier study carried out by Peters and Person (2021) whose study revealed that stakeholder engagement strategy is considered as an effective vehicle that help to carry out the proper decision-making for obtaining and showing of gratification by increasing the degree of harmonization and enhance the overall performance of the organization.

CONCLUSION

Based on the strength of the findings, the study concluded that the Nigerian Agip Oil Company designed its stakeholder's engagement strategy to accommodate the company and the host communities. The study also concluded that there is a connect between stakeholders' engagement strategy and stakeholders expectations because it addressed the expectation of the people. More so, the study concluded that stakeholders' engagement strategy of Nigerian Agip Oil Company is in line with conventional practices.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. That there is need for companies and organizations to have a formidable stakeholders engagement strategy that will impact on the company and host communities.
2. That it is good and relevant for an organizations stakeholders engagement strategy to have a connection with stakeholders expectations by addressing the MOU between the company and the host communities.
3. That companies and organizations should ensure that they employ the services of professionals in the conception and implementation of the strategies.

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